

A REVIEW ON *KUSHTAGHNA DRAVYAS* IN *SHAKHA VARGA* OF *BHAVAPRAKASHA NIGHANTU*

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ABSTRACT

The increasing prevalence of Skin diseases due to unhealthy eating practice of current situation, hence there is need to explore drugs which can be used in daily diet to prevent possible skin diseases or it can be used as a diet in patient suffering from skin disease. Hence, exploring on the *Shaka Varga* of *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, focusing mainly on 12 *Kushtaghna Dravyas* out of total 71 drugs. These 12 drugs are critically analyzed through their *Rasapanchaka* and how potentially these drugs are useful in prevention and treatment of Skin diseases.

KEYWORDS: *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu*, *Kushtaghna*, Skin diseases, *Shaka Varga*.

INTRODUCTION

Bhavaprakasha Nighantu is one of the most authoritative texts of *Ayurveda* and forms part of the *Laghutrayi* (the triad of concise Ayurvedic treatises). Composed by *Acharya Bhavamishra* during the 15th-16th century CE, this work was originally titled *Haritakyadi Nighantu*. The text systematically classifies medicinal plants and substances into 23 *Vargas* (groups), beginning with *Haritakyadi Varga* and concluding with *Anekartha Varga*.

Among these, the ninth group — *Shaka Varga* — is devoted to vegetables and edible herbs, elaborating on their pharmacological properties (*Guna–Karma*), therapeutic uses, and dietary significance. Interestingly, *Acharya Bhavamishra* attributes *Kustaghna Karma* (Anti-skin disease activity) to several herbs within this group, indicating their potential role in managing *Kushtha* (a broad term encompassing various skin disorders).

In contemporary times, skin diseases have become a major global health concern, affecting individuals both physically and psychologically due to their chronic nature and impact on appearance. Modern dermatological treatments, though effective, are often associated with adverse drug reactions^[1] and high relapse rates, which highlights the need for safer, natural, and holistic alternatives.

Ayurveda, with its vast pharmacopoeia of herbs and detailed understanding of *Kushtha Chikitsa*, offers promising options for managing skin ailments. The dietary and medicinal plants described in *Shaka Varga* may serve as both therapeutic and preventive agents due to their *Kustaghna*, *Rasayana*, and *Pitta–Kapha–Shamaka* properties.

METHODOLOGY

- Data is collected from *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu (Shaka Varga)*, other *Ayurvedic* texts like *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, other *Nighantus* and contemporary Author books for cross reference, only drugs having indication for *Kustaghna Karma* are included from the drugs mentioned in *Shaka Varga* from *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* for critical analysis.
- Online data is collected from databases like Pubmed, Google Scholar, and relevant Research journals.

Table 1: Rasapanchaka of Kushtaghna Dravyas of Shaka Varga.^[2]

S.N	Name of the Drug	Botanical Name	Rasadipanchaka	Karma & Rogagnata
1.	<i>Changeri Patra</i>	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	<i>Rasa: Amla</i> <i>Guna : Ruksha, Ushna</i> <i>Veerya : Ushna</i> <i>Vipaka: Amla</i> <i>Doshagnata : Kapha, Vata, Samaka</i>	<i>Agnideepaka, Rucikara, Kustaghna, Arsoghna, Grahanihara Rogagnata: Kushta, Aruchi, Arshas, Grahani</i>
2.	<i>Hilamochika Patra</i>	<i>Enhydra fluctuans</i> Lour.	<i>Rasa: Tikta</i> ^[3] <i>Veerya : Seeta</i> <i>Vipaka: Katu</i> <i>Doshagnata: Kapha, Pitta, Samaka.</i>	<i>Sothahara, Kustaghna. Rogagnata: Shotha, Kushta</i>
3.	<i>Sitivara Patra</i>	<i>Marsilea</i>	<i>Rasa: Swadu, Kasaya</i>	<i>Kustaghna, Vrishya, Jwarahara, Swasahara,</i>

		<i>quadrifolia</i> L.	Guna: Laghu, Ruksa Veerya: Seeta Vipaka: Katu ^[4] Doshagnata: Tridosha Samaka	Pramehaghna, Medohara, Rucikara Rogagnata: Kushta, Jwara, Prameha, Swasa, Klaibya
4.	Dadrughna Patra	<i>Cassia tora</i> L.	Rasa: Amla Guna: Laghu and Ruksa Veerya: Usna Vipaka: Katu Doshagnata: Vata, Kapha Samaka.	Kustaghna, Kandughna, Swasahara, Kasahara, Krimighna. Rogagnata: Kushta, Kandu, Swasa, kasa and Krimi.
5.	Gojivha Patra	<i>Onosma bracteatum</i> Wall.	Rasa: Kasaya, Tikta, Madhura Guna: Laghu, Mridu. Veerya: Seeta Vipaka: Madhura Doshagnata: Vatala, Kapha Pittahara.	Kustaghna, Pramehaghna, Raktavikarahara, Mutrakrichrahara, Jwarahara. Rogagnata: Kushta, Prameha, Mutrakrichra, Jwara
6.	Guduchi Patra	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.)	Rasa: Kasaya, Katu, Tiktam Guna: Laghu Veerya: Ushna Vipaka: Madhura Doshagnata: Tridoshasamaka.	Kustaghna, Panduhara, Mehaghna, Vataraktahara, Kamalahara, Dahasamaka, Sangrahi, Rasayana. Rogagnata: Kushta, Pandu, Prameha, Vatarakta, Kamala, Daha, Atisara
7.	Patola Patra	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> Roxb.	Rasa: Tikta Guna: Laghu, Snigdha Veerya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu ^[5] Doshagnata: Tridoshasamaka	Kustaghna, Pacana, Hridya, Vrishya, Agnideepaka, Kasahara, Jwarahara, Krimighna. Rogagnata: Kushta, Jwara, Krimi, Kasa, Klaibya
	Patola Phala		Rasa: Tikta Guna: Laghu Veerya: Ushna Vipaka: Madhura ^[6] Doshagnata: Tridoshasamaka	Kushtaha, Pacana, Vrishya, Agnideepaka, Kasabhanjana. Rogagnata: Kushta, Agnimandhya, Kasa
8.	Shobanjana Phala	<i>Moringa olifera</i> Lam.	Rasa: Madhura, Kasaya Guna: Ruksa Veerya: Ushna Doshagnata: Kapha, Pitta Samaka.	Sulahara, Kushtaghna, Swasahara, Gulmahara, Ksayahara, Deepana. Rogagnata: Sula, Kushta, Swasa, Gulma, Ksaya
9.	Karkoti Phala	<i>Mormordica dioca</i> Roxb.	Rasa: Madhura ^[7] Guna: Laghu Veerya: Sheeta ^[8] Vipaka: Katu Doshagnata: Tridoshasamaka ^[7]	Kushtaghna, Agnideepaka, Swasahara, Kasahara, Jwarahara, Hrillasahara. Rogagnata: Kushta, Swasa, Kasa, Jwara, Hrillasa
10.	Sarshapa Nala	<i>Brassica juncea</i> Linn.	Guna: Tiksna, Ushna Veerya: Ushna Doshagnata: Vata, Kapha, Hara	Kushtaghna, Kandughna, Vranahara, Krimihara, Dadrughna, Rucikara Rogagnata: Kushta, Kandu, Vrana, Krimi, Aruci, Dadrukushta.
11.	Varahi Kandha	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	Rasa: Katu, Tikta Guna: Laghu, Snigdha Veerya: Seeta ^[9] Vipaka: Katu ^[10] Doshagnata: Vatahara, Pittala.	Kushtaghna, Mehaghna, Rasayana, Agnideepaka, Sukrala, Balya. Rogagnata: Kushta, Prameha, Agnimandhya, Dourbalya, Shukrakshaya.
12.	Kemuka Kandha	<i>Costus speciosus</i> (J. Koenig) Sm.	Rasa: Tikta Guna: Laghu Veerya: Seeta Vipaka: Katu Doshagnata: Vatakara.	Kushtaghna, Mehaghna, Rasayana, Agnideepaka, Sukrala, Balya. Rogagnata: Kushta, Prameha, Atisara, Agnimandhya

DISCUSSION

Majority of the drug possess *Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura Rasa. Laghu, Ruksha Guna. Seeta Veerya* and *Pitta Kapha Shamaka* properties, which are opposite qualities against *Pitta Dosha*, as the *Vyadhi Kushta is Pitta Pradhana Tridoshaja Vyadhi*. Hence above mentioned drugs will be very useful in case of *Kushta* as *Aushadha Dravya* or *Pathya*. In recent research Some of the above mentioned drug have proven for its Antifungal, Antipsoriatic and Antiallergic activity which are the common Pathology involved in the formation of Skin diseases, these are as follows below.

1. **Hilamochika:** In-vitro antifungal study conducted on methanol and acetone extract of *Enhydra fluctans* Lour. As shown Antifungal activity against fungi like *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigates* and *Fusarium* SP. which are commonly involved fungi in pathology of Skin diseases.^[11]

2. **Sitivara:** In-vitro antifungal study conducted on diethyl ether leaf and stem extract of *Marsilea quadrifolia*. showed potent Antifungal activity on fungal strains like *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus Flavus*, *Aspergillus terreus*, *Trichoderma viride* and *Fusarium solani*. which are commonly involved fungi in pathology of Skin diseases.^[12]

3. **Dadrughnapatra:** In-vivo Antipsoriatic study conducted on Ultraviolet (UV)-B- induced Psoriasis in the Rat. The O/W (oil in water) cream of *Cassia tora L.* has shown potent Antipsoriatic activity against UV-B- induced Psoriasis of Rat. The activity may aided due to presence of phytoconstituents like glycoside, essential oil and aloe-emodin which posses Antioxidant properties.^[13]

4. **Karkoti:** In-vivo Antiallergic study conducted on the hapten induced skin allergy or damage in 5week old Male NC/Nga mice. The water extract of *Mormordica dioca* flesh has shown Anti-allergic activity by inhibiting histamine release from A23187 treated KU812 cells and decreasing the level of IgE level in Serum from Mice.^[14]

5. **Kemuka:** In-vitro antifungal study conducted on Methanol, Ethylacetate and Hexane extract of Tuber of *Costus speciosa* has showm Potent against fungi like *Candida albicans*, *Candida glabrata*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida krusei* and *Candida parapsilosis*. This is due to presence of phytochemical like Terpenoids, Phenols and Alkaloids mainly for exhibiting potential Antifungal activity.^[15]

6. Varahikanda: In-vitro antifungal study conducted on the Aqueous and Methanol and Ethanol extract of *Dioscorea bulbifera* L. Tuber as shown potent Antifungal activity against *Candida parapsilosis* (MTCC 2513) due to presence phytochemicals like Alkaloids, Glycosides, Sterols, Polyphenols, Flavonoids Contributing to its medicinal use.^[16]

CONCLUSION

The *Shaka Varga* of *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* contains several herbs with potential *Kushtaghna* activity, pharmacological actions like Antifungal, Antiallergic and Antioxidant Justifying their judicial use as *Pathya* or *Aushadha* to prevent or cure the Skin diseases. Integrating classical wisdom with modern evidence can lead to safe, effective and holistic Management of Skin diseases. Which allows the patient to avoid unwanted exposure to Adverse effect caused by Artificial medicines.

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